

6G-Path

D.7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Document Summary Information

Project number:	101139172		
Project Title	6G-PATH: 6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe		
Acronym	6G-PATH		
Start Date	1 January 2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.6gpath.eu		
Deliverable	D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan		
Work Package	WP7		
Contractual due date	M6, 30 June 2024	Actual submission date	
Type	R — Document, report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	eBOS		
Responsible Author	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)		
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Co-funded by
the European Union

6G-PATH project has received funding from the Smart Networks

and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101139172.

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Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.1	31/03/2024	Initial deliverable structure	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v0.2	30/04/2024	50% of the deliverable content	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v0.3	29/05/2024	90% of the deliverable content	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v0.4	30/05/2024	Document Internal Review	Philippos Philippou (eBOS)
v0.5	31/05/2024	100% of the deliverable content	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v0.6	12/06/2024	Document Internal Review	Imesha Wedikkara Gedara (UBRAD), Andy Edmonds (TER), Luís Cordeiro (ONE), Ioannis Chochliouros (OTE)
v0.7	13/06/2024	Amendments based on suggested revisions & Final version for Quality Review	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v0.8	14/06/2024	First revisions after the final review	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)
v1.0	18/06/2024	Final version for submission	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	The Fifth Generation of (Mobile and Wireless) Communications
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
5GWF	5G World Forum
6G	The Sixth Generation of Communications
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AAA	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIAI	Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovation
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation
ACM	Association for Computer Machinery
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
CARIE	Cyprus Association of Research and Innovation Enterprises
CCW	Critical Communications World
CSUR	Computing Surveys
CYTED	Ibero-American Program of Science and Technology for Development
D2D	Device to Device
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
DCM	Dissemination & Communication Manager
EC	European Commission
ECCWS	European Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security
ECSO	European cyber security Organization
EMEA	Europe, Middle-East and Africa
ETC	European Telemedicine Conference
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and communications
GA	Grant Agreement
GIoT	Global IoT Summit
HE	Horizon Europe
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
IET	Institution of Engineering and Technology
GSMA	Global system for Mobile Communications Association
ICC	International Conference on Communications
ICCE	International Conference on Consumer Electronics
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ICTS4eHealth	IEEE International Conference on ICT Solutions for eHealth
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IFIP	International Federation for Information Processing
IJCIP	International Journal for Critical Infrastructure Protection
IoT	Internet of Things
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KTN	Knowledge Transfer Network
LCN	Local Computer Networks
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
M	Month/s

MWC	Mobile World Congress
NCA	Network Computing and Applications
NEM	New European Media
NESSI	Networked Software and Services Initiative
NGI	Next Generation Internet
NOMS	Network operations and Management Symposium
OpenRAN	Open Radio Access Network
PIMRC	Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PSCE	Public Safety Communication Europe
R&D	Research and Development
SEPR	Search Engine Page Ranking
SIGCOMM	Special Interest Group on Data Communications
SICSA	Scottish Informatics and Computer Science Alliance
SME	Small- and Medium-sized Enterprise
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
TCCA	The Critical Communications Association
TV	Television
UN	United Nations
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VR	Virtual Reality
WCNC	Wireless Communications and Networking Conference
WF-IoT	World Forum on Internet of Things
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WWW, www	World Wide Web
XR	eXtended Reality

Executive Summary

This document offers a comprehensive insight into the dissemination and communication strategies of the 6G-PATH project. Beginning with an introduction that maps out project outputs and outlines the report's structure, it progresses to discuss dissemination activities, target groups and channels.

Communication activities and their corresponding target groups and channels are detailed, followed by an overview of the awareness-raising strategy aimed at promoting project objectives and technological advancements.

Guidelines for conducting dissemination and communication activities, including email addresses and announcements, are provided. Additionally, metrics and quantifiable targets for monitoring outcomes are outlined, while the details of the major dissemination activities that have been achieved are also presented.

Concluding with insights into the next steps and conclusions, the report serves as a valuable guide for implementing effective dissemination and communication strategies within the 6G-PATH project.

1 Introduction

The deliverable D7.2, titled “Dissemination and Communication Plan”, is linked to task T7.1, “Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activities” (led by eBOS) under WP7. Its purpose is to carry out the dissemination, communication and impact assessment efforts regarding the project’s objectives, reports, results, achievements and other outcomes. The activity is in line with “Objective 6” outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), which focuses on disseminating and communicating results to a broad spectrum of stakeholders, while also ensuring an impact on standardization endeavours [1].

Specifically, this initial deliverable on dissemination and communication activities outlines the intended audience, spanning from the general public to scientific and academic communities, as well as specific 6G stakeholders and market participants. It also establishes the channels and methods for dissemination and communication, along with a comprehensive awareness raising strategy that is discerned into three phases and covers various “key” activities. This strategy is designed to achieve widespread visibility and foster engagement with stakeholders across multiple levels.

This deliverable lays the groundwork for subsequent reports, namely D7.3 and D7.4, “Dissemination, Commercialization and Standardization” (initial and final versions respectively), which will provide detailed accounts of the dissemination and communication activities conducted throughout the project duration.

1.1 Mapping 6G-PATH outputs

This section aims to “map out” the commitments outlined in the 6G-PATH GA, both within the formal descriptions of Deliverables and Tasks in relation to the outputs and activities executed within the project.

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

6G-PATH GA Component Title	6G-PATH GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D7.2 Dissemination and Communication plan</i>			
<i>Reports on the activities plan towards dissemination, communication, and impact assessment</i>			
TASKS			
<i>T7.1 – Dissemination and communication plan and activities</i>	“This task aims to enhance the dissemination of project outcomes, particularly in scientific and innovative aspects, to both the general public and scientific community. The activities will be carried out through a well-designed dissemination strategy and Data Management Plan. Specifically, the objectives of this task are: (i) to establish and maintain a link with the general public and specialized communities through a public website, which will provide information on the consortium, project objectives, main outcomes, public deliverables and specific social networks; (ii) to participate in industry-led white papers and	Chapter 2: Dissemination activities Chapter 3: Communication activities Chapter 4: Awareness raising strategy Chapter 5: Dissemination and Communication guidelines Chapter 6: Dissemination and Communication metrics and quantifiable targets	The document offers a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication strategies adopted within the 6G-PATH project, including meticulously crafted plans and guidelines for implementation. In particular, it covers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination activities, along with target groups, objectives and identified channels for effectively disseminating project outputs. Communication activities that are designed to engage stakeholders, outlining objectives, target groups and chosen channels for effective communication. A comprehensive awareness raising strategy to promote project objectives, scope and targets

	<p>create project-specific white papers to highlight the benefits of the project’s approaches, impact on use cases, and business cases from external parties, which will be made available and disseminated in a targeted approach using the partners’ established business and collaboration channels; (iii) to publish joint articles in major scientific conferences and high-impact journals to disseminate the designs, architecture, specific solutions and their evaluation, which will be made available on the project website and focused on open access venues in compliance with EC open policy; (iv) to organize demonstrators at industry venues and trade shows to showcase the innovative aspects of the project and potential industry impact; (v) to organize workshops, tutorials and seminars locally and internationally to address the scientific community, and; (vi) to encourage contributions to open-source software initiatives. [...] Main outcomes: project website and social media channels setup (achieved in D7.1); D&C plan (reported in D7.2); D&C deliverable reporting the D&C activities carried out during the project (reported in D7.3 and D7.4).”</p>		<p>technological advancements across stakeholders and industries.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines and protocols for conducting dissemination and communication activities, including information on email addresses, announcements and relevant guidelines.
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1.2 Deliverable overview and report structure

The report is structured into seven chapters, as explained below.

- Chapter 1 provides context for the deliverable and outlines its objectives. It includes sub-sections such as “Mapping 6G-PATH outputs” and “Deliverable overview and report structure”.
- Chapter 2 elaborates on the dissemination activities planned within the project. It discusses the target groups, objectives and channels identified for disseminating project outputs effectively.
- Chapter 3 focuses on the communication activities designed to engage with various stakeholders. It outlines the objectives, target groups and communication channels chosen for effective communication.
- Chapter 4 presents the comprehensive awareness raising strategy devised to promote the objectives, scope and technological advancements of the 6G-PATH project across “key” stakeholders and industries.
- Chapter 5 provides guidelines and protocols for conducting dissemination and communication activities. It includes information on internal communication procedures, email addresses for dissemination, announcements of upcoming publications and other relevant guidelines.

- Chapter 6 outlines the framework for monitoring the outcomes, metrics and quantifiable targets related to dissemination and communication activities. It also includes the achieved KPIs along with the details of major dissemination activities that have been achieved so far.
- The final chapter (Chapter 7) summarizes the key insights from the deliverable and outlines the next steps and conclusions drawn from the analysis of dissemination and communication activities.

Overall, this deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication strategies adopted within the 6G-PATH project, along with detailed plans and guidelines for effective implementation.

2 Dissemination activities

2.1 Dissemination target groups

The overarching goal of the collaborative 6G-PATH dissemination strategy is to share project outcomes that can serve as “building blocks” for the target stakeholders’ audience to advance their respective endeavours. In essence, the aim is to leverage the knowledge generated by 6G-PATH, fostering progress in technology, science, industry and policy. 6G-PATH has identified several target stakeholders, as outlined in Table 2. Tailored joint dissemination efforts will be designed to align with the requirements and characteristics of each stakeholder group for effective dissemination.

Table 2: Dissemination target groups and respective activities

Main dissemination target groups	Activities
Telecom operators and vertical industries in healthcare, education, smart cities and farming	An open dialogue will be established via the project’s website as well as through the organization of focused group meetings in order for the 6G-PATH project to “better address” their needs and demands and to integrate their feedback at “key” points of the project as well as to engage them.
Scientific community, in the field of B5G/6G, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR, OpenRAN	Partners will reach this community using their contacts and cooperation with other research projects by participating in scientific conferences and publishing in scientific journals.
Policy makers and regulatory bodies with a “key” role in influencing strategic choices for B5G/6G technology evolutions	An open dialogue will be launched to highlight major aspects of the 6G-PATH concept and receive feedback for further investigation. 6G-PATH along with the European Commission will try to get in touch with the relevant actors.

6G-PATH has also identified a number of specific stakeholders as target audience for the advancement, assessment, adoption and utilization of the results achieved through 6G-PATH. These are listed in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Specific key stakeholders identified as target audience

Industry/SMEs	Scientific Community	Facilitators/Enablers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telecom operators • Vertical industries • Software industries and applications developers • Industrial associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific communities of software engineering, beyond 5G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Related EU-funded projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Institutions (EU Commission, EU Science foundation) • 5GPPP, 6G-IA • Standardization bodies • Regional and national regulators and policy makers including telecoms and digital governance departments, municipalities, LEAs

2.2 Dissemination channels

A significant aspect of disseminating information involves collectively and cooperatively participating in relevant initiatives of the 5G-PPP and the 6G Infrastructure Association (6G-IA). 6G-PATH will contribute to materials such as the European 5G Annual Journal, the 6G-IA projects brochure and other requested materials, including videos, coordinated at the 6G-IA level.

Moreover, 6G-PATH has identified “channels” to disseminate project results to scientific, technological and industrial communities. The dissemination activities will be customized to suit the requirements, stakeholders and

events selected for dissemination. Specifically, the target audience and dissemination channels will be actively monitored and chosen to maximize impact in geographical regions corresponding to partners' planned activities. Table 4 outlines the target audience and channels.

Table 4: Dissemination channels

Target audience	Channels
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Vertical Industries 	Workshops at conferences (e.g., EuCNC event, IEEE Global Comms Conference, IEEE International Conference on Comms, IEEE Conference on Computer Comms, ACM SIGCOMM, MWC, IEEE 5G Summit, Forging a Sustainable Path to 6G, Advanced Solutions for 6G Satellite Systems).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Vertical Industries 	On-site demonstrations to showcase selected trials and pilots' experiments.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR 	Scientific papers in workshops, conferences, and journals e.g., EuCNC event, IEEE Global Comms Conference, IEEE International Conference on Comms, IEEE Conference on Computer Comms, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics, IEEE Comms Magazine, International Journal of Computer and Telecommunications Networking, 5G Annual Journal.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Vertical Industries 	Social networks posts to take advantage of modern communication channels for wider dissemination.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telecom operators • SMEs • Vertical Industries 	Participation in trade fairs showcasing project's solutions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Vertical Industries 	Project web site , providing scientific papers, public project deliverables and software tools.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in software engineering, B5G/6G, Satellite Communications, IoT, AI, AR/VR/XR • Vertical Industries 	Open events with free access , where experimenters will exchange experiences and provide input for future requirements.
Researchers in the project technologies and the four verticals	Clustering activities and knowledge transfer meetings with other relevant projects from SNS JU, HE and other B5G/6G tracks.
Researchers in the project technologies and the four verticals	Open access datasets from project internal and third-party experiments made available.

2.3 Other dissemination channels to be used

In addition to the channels explained above, 6G-PATH will also leverage additional dissemination avenues in order for the project to broaden its outreach and engage with diverse audiences to maximize its impact and achieve its objectives. These additional dissemination channels are:

2.3.1 Logo and templates

A standardized template and logo (cf. Figure 1) have been developed to establish the project's identity/branding, which will be uniformly applied across all project presentations and publications.

Figure 1: 6G-PATH logo

2.3.2 Online presence

A modern and interactive website for 6G-PATH (<https://6gpath.eu>) has been designed and managed by eBOS (Month 3), functioning as a central hub for disseminating project details and outcomes to the public. The website will undergo regular updates and leverages various social media tools such as LinkedIn and X (former Twitter) to share project news, results, upcoming events, etc., and foster engagement with target audiences. Within this framework, style guidelines have been established by eBOS to govern the visual identity (including font selection, image placement, colour schemes, styles, etc.) of the project, ensuring consistency across the website's various components. The website's homepage is illustrated in Figure 2. A comprehensive overview of the project website is provided in D7.1 ("Project website") which was submitted during Month 3 of the project.

Figure 2: 6G-PATH website homepage

2.3.3 Social networks

- 6G-PATH utilizes various online social networking platforms, namely LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/6g-path>), X – former Twitter (<https://x.com/6gpath>) and YouTube

(<https://www.youtube.com/@6gpath>) to establish a dynamic interaction channel between project members and both technical and public audiences. Starting from month M1, the consortium consistently shares updates and engages in discussions. Content is periodically refreshed and feedback gathered plays a significant role in “shaping” the project’s trajectory. This endeavour is overseen by eBOS. The social media channels for the 6G-PATH project are illustrated in Figure 3 (LinkedIn), Figure 4 (X – former Twitter) and Figure 5 (YouTube).

Figure 3: 6G-PATH LinkedIn page

Figure 4: 6G-PATH X (former Twitter) page

Figure 5: 6G-PATH YouTube page

2.3.4 Printed material and posters

Printed material and posters (will) serve as effective dissemination channels by providing tangible resources for conveying project information. These marketing materials, including posters and roll-up banners, offer a visual representation of key project details, such as objectives, outcomes and contact information. They will be particularly useful for showcasing project achievements at conferences, workshops and other events, capturing the attention of attendees and sparking interest in the project. Additionally, posters and roll-up banners will be strategically placed in high-traffic areas to increase visibility and awareness among target audiences. By leveraging printed materials, 6G-PATH can enhance its outreach efforts and effectively communicate its message to a broader audience. A roll-up banner (Figure 6 below) has already been designed, as well as 7 posters that present the project’s general information, a generalized conceptual approach, the open call #1 and the four verticals (Figures 7-13). These posters were prominently featured during our project’s participation at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024 event, held from 3rd to 6th June 2024 in Antwerp, Belgium.

Figure 6: 6G-PATH roll-up banner

Figure 7: 6G-PATH general poster

Figure 8: 6G-PATH conceptual poster

6G-Path 6g-path @6gpath @6gpath www.6gpath.eu

6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe
Join the Innovation Journey with 6G-PATH
 Are you ready to shape the future of telecommunications?

6G-PATH Open Call #1
 Call for proposals for the development of ground-breaking services and applications for deployment in a cutting-edge infrastructure.

Why Participate?

- 1** **Contribute to 6G Infrastructure:** Be at the forefront of the next generation of communication technology.
- 2** **EU Industry Leadership:** Strengthen EU's position in the global tech landscape.
- 3** **Support and Funding:** Gain support and funding for your innovative projects.

Tracks Available:

Track A: Infrastructure Deployment

- Open to all entities capable of setting up 5G/6G network infrastructures.
- 2 projects with a maximum grant of €300k.
- 8-month project + 12-month support duration.

Track B: Infrastructure Extensions

- Open to all entities capable of integrating advances into 5G/6G infrastructures.
- 10 projects with a maximum grant of €60k.
- 6-month project + 14-month support duration.

Who Can Apply?
 Individual or Consortia of 2 entities.

Important Information:
 Open Call #1, running from
01 September 2024 to 31 October 2024 (17h00 CEST).
 Projects will be continuously supported by the core consortium for seamless integration and validation. Visit www.6gpath.eu website for more details and application guidelines.
Don't Miss Out on This Opportunity to Shape the Future!
opencall@6gpath.eu

Consortium

Co-funded by the European Union SNS

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Figure 9: 6G-PATH open call #1 poster

6G-Path 6g-path @6gpath @6gpath www.6gpath.eu

Large Scale Use Case Trials
Enhanced Monitoring and Productivity in Farming Environments

Enhanced Vineyard Management and Productivity Enabled by 5G/6G

Crates: Edge Computing Nodes with Private 5G/6G Networks
 Terraview OS: Cloud-Based Vineyard Management Platform
 AAVs and AGVs: Autonomous Aerial and Ground Vehicles for Operations
 Awareness Solution: Machinery Tracking Solution Bridging Decisions Between Terraview OS and Operations

Automated Decision Making of Irrigation of an Open Avocado Fruit Orchard via Phenology Monitoring

- Network of (battery-powered) sensors and actuators to manage water content of the soil-plant-atmosphere continuum
- Compare stressed and unstressed plants to test water demands of avocado crops and improve the precision of irrigation
- Monitor the phenological state of the crops through images and videos transmitted in real-time by drones
- Use of different types of artificial vision cameras designed for agriculture

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Figure 10: 6G-PATH poster on Farming vertical

www.6gpath.eu

Large Scale Use Case Trials

6G Enabled Education for Enhanced Learning Experiences

XR Rural School

6G technology to improve rural education in Romania with XR-enabled interactive learning.

Key Focus Areas Include:

- **Immersive Education:** Creating engaging and interactive learning environments
- **Technology Accessibility:** Ensuring students in rural areas have access to advanced educational technology
- **Customized learning:** Tailoring educational experiences to individual student needs
- **Teacher Empowerment:** Providing tools and training for teachers to effectively use XR technology
- **Performance Improvement:** Boost academic performance among rural students

Classroom of the Future

The Classroom of the Future focuses on teaching and learning of complicated 5G/6G virtualised, softwareised and multi-tenant infrastructures.

The Main Actors of this Scenario will be:

- Testbed Operator
- Teaching staff as End-User
- Students as End-Users

Expected Outcomes:

- Driving 6G Development
- Improved Learning Outcomes.
- Enhanced Collaborative Learning
- Enhanced Accessibility

XR Health Training

Healthcare education includes training with manikins, which simulate human anatomy and physiology, providing students with lifelike learning experiences.

With Help of Technologies Towards 6G the Aim is to:

- Extend manikin training beyond a confined location
- Allowing the manikin to be remotely controlled
- Allowing students to take part in the simulated scenarios remotely.

This will allow more authentic and enhanced learning experiences and improve the flexibility in the education.

Consortium

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Figure 11: 6G-PATH poster on Education vertical

www.6gpath.eu

Large Scale Use Case Trials

Secure and Reliable Connectivity & Communication for Personalised Remote Care

Personalised Care for Chronic Wound 3D Scanning and Customised Patch Bioprinting

- Nomadic node for enabling connectivity of nurse Apps and devices
- Secure exchange of 3D models of wound 3D patch model
- and wound parameters computing (depth, volume)

Elderly Monitoring and Prevention by Fall Prediction and Rehab@Home

- 5G Connectivity at Home
- Secure exchange of video recordings and fine granular sensor data
- Continuous fall prediction risk assessment for fragile persons
- Localisation indoor & outdoor, especially for mentally impaired

Consortium

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Figure 12: 6G-PATH poster on Health vertical

Figure 13: 6G-PATH poster on Smart Cities vertical

2.3.5 Project brochure

The project brochure, in the form of a booklet, will serve as a pivotal dissemination tool and its distribution at various relevant events will enhance visibility and foster engagement with stakeholders. This brochure will encapsulate essential project details, including objectives, methodologies and anticipated outcomes, providing recipients with a comprehensive overview of 6G-PATH’s endeavours. By disseminating copies of the brochure at conferences, workshops, trade fairs and other relevant events, the project will maximize its reach and effectively communicate its value proposition to a wide spectrum of users, practitioners and technicians.

2.3.6 White papers

6G-PATH will participate in industry-led white papers and create project-specific documents. These white papers will offer insights into the project’s approaches, highlighting their benefits, impact on use cases and endorsements from external parties. They will be disseminated through partners’ established business and collaboration channels, ensuring targeted distribution to interested parties.

2.4 Dissemination activities per partner

Within the framework of the 6G-PATH project, each partner plays a crucial role in executing dissemination activities aimed at effectively sharing project outcomes with relevant stakeholders. Table 5 below offers an overview of the dissemination efforts that will be undertaken by each partner, highlighting their specific contributions and approaches to disseminating project results. By exploring the dissemination activities per partner, insights emerge into the collaborative efforts driving the dissemination strategy of the 6G-PATH project.

Table 5: Planned dissemination activities per partner

Partner	Planned dissemination activities
OTE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant role in market, offering innovative network solutions and services focused on 5G and beyond 5G (B5G). • Robust involvement in dissemination activities, spreading project outcomes widely across Greece and internationally via OTE Group of Companies and DT Group of Companies. • Participation in business- and academic-oriented events. • Collaboration with academia and research institutes for valuable publications in international journals and conferences. • Engagement in relevant European and international fora and events. • Support for technical demonstrations and trials. • Organization of at least one international workshop per year to jointly promote innovative project results. • Participation in exhibitions and industrial events (e.g., EuCNC, MWC, EU Concertation events, etc.). • Prioritization of collaborations with other EU-funded projects.
ICT-FI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of project outcomes in selected high-impact journals and magazines on communications/networking/cloud computing, along with reputed international conferences and vertical-oriented publications, in close collaboration with project partners. • Dissemination of project findings among business partners. • Publication of project results as scientific articles in international conference proceedings and journals, prioritizing Open Access whenever possible. • Holding business meetings with companies such as NOKIA, LENOVO and Ericsson Finland. • Potential target journals and magazines: IEEE Network Magazine, IEEE Internet of Things and IEEE Trans. Mobile Computing. • Potential target conferences: IEEE Globecom, ICC, WCNC, and EuCNC.
ORO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination target groups: Romanian Technical Universities' students, assistants and professors, as well as end-users from the business sector and public sector SMEs, and high-tech entrepreneurs. • Dissemination of project results within Orange Corporate and Orange affiliates. • Dissemination of project outcomes and ambitions through the Orange Educational Program, with at least 2 technical workshops involving a minimum of 1,500 students and academic staff from major universities in Romania. • Dissemination to start-ups and SMEs through collaboration with Innovation Labs, a university-anchored national pre-accelerator program and Orang Fab, an acceleration program supporting existing high-tech start-ups and SMEs to enhance their products and expand their customer base.
TdE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in Telecom industry events like MWC, 5G FORUM. • Demos and showcases with vertical industries and users. • Participation in national events organized by the 6G program UNICO I+D in Spain.
ALB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication of project objectives and outcomes in technical conferences and business-based events. • Dissemination across various social media platforms. • Presentation of project objectives and results to all Altice Group.

ADS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in various Public Protection & Disaster Relief (PPDR) events and communication about the project and its achievements. • Examples of events: TCCA Critical Communications World (CCW), French Fire Brigades annual congress, and Public Safety Communication Europe (PSCE) conferences.
UMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in scientific events and journals to present B5G innovations. • Support for partners to present demos and showcases with vertical industries and users. • Target scientific events: PIMRC, EuCNC, Computer Networks, or IEEE Network. • Demos to be presented at MWC, 5G Forum, or national events organized by 6G programa UNICO I+D in Spain.
FOKUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of project results through scientific conferences and journals such as IEEE ICTS4eHealth, ICT4AgingWell, IEEE Globecom, and IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing. • Participation and demonstration of project results in industry-oriented events such as GSMA Mobile World Congress. • Inclusion of specific presentations and demonstrations as part of Fraunhofer's FUSECO Forum industry R&D oriented event.
KAU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of technical and healthcare results produced within 6G-PATH. • Joint publications in high-quality scientific journals and leading international conferences such as IEEE Transaction on Mobile Computing, Intensive and Critical Care Nursing, IEEE Globecom and IEEE Communications Magazine. • Contribution to the organization of international workshops. • Support for the consortium in demonstrating the 6G-PATH results at events such as EuCNC. • Dissemination of results from eHealth and healthcare education trials to stakeholders in the healthcare and healthcare education domain. • Arrangement of one or more stakeholder workshops to present and demonstrate 6G-PATH results. • Utilization of the partner network available through Digital Well Arena, a national initiative around digitalization of healthcare services, as well as strong contacts within healthcare at the Health Department. • Dissemination of results to engineering and nursing students. • Integration of results and use cases from 6G-PATH into relevant courses within undergraduate and graduate education. • Offering student theses in project-related topics. • Dissemination of results on low latency communication solutions and APIs to relevant working groups within the IETF/IRTF.
IT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific dissemination through conference and journal publications. • Laboratory prototypes. • City-scale prototype. • Final demonstrator with mechanisms proposed for edge and cloud technology and use cases results. • Dissemination through MSc and PhD Theses in the scope of the project. • Integration of high-qualified individuals into the industry worldwide. • Participation in international conferences, workshops, and exhibitions to promote the project. • Publications in international journals and conferences, including IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials, IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing, IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics, Journal

	<p>of Network and Systems Management, Security and Communication Networks, Elsevier IJCIP, IEEE/IFIP NOMS, LCN, NCA, European Conference on Cyber Warfare and Security (ECCWS), and IEEE Globecom.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aveiro Living Lab to demonstrate benefits of technologies under real usage situations to technical and non-technical audiences. • Organization of workshops and/or special sessions in training contexts and international/national conferences for wider dissemination.
ONE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of project results in several venues such as IEEE Communications Magazine, ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR), IFIP/IEEE International Symposium on Integrated Network Management (IM). • Preference for joint papers reflecting collaboration with other project partners. • Support for the consortium in dissemination and demonstration of the 6G-PATH concept and results. • Participation in industry events such as MWC, Critical Communications World industry events and others.
RedZinc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of information videos. • Utilization of own social media and website. • Creation of two white papers related to internal experiments in healthcare and production of an associated informational video. • Attendance at healthcare conferences such as European Telemedicine Conference (ETC). • Promotion of newly developed products at healthcare conferences. • Dissemination of information to the healthcare sector and 6G-IA through website and social media.
OdinS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of innovative results of the 6G-PATH project such as new security, privacy and trust mechanisms (e.g., SecurityaaS services, AAA component, Policy Enforcer). • Involvement of postdoctoral staff and PhD industrial students in research and dissemination activities. • Dissemination target groups: customers, research community, IoT/6G industry and international associations (e.g., AIOTI, IoT-Forum, 6G-AI, FIWARE, IETF, ETSI, ECSO WG1). • Active involvement of Dr. Skarmeta, CIO of the company, in conference and workshop organization like 5GWF, GloT, WF-IoT Globecom, etc. And push for possible panel and workshop organization.
eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion and wide dissemination of the project's results towards European ICT SMEs enabling the visibility and encouragement of the use of project's exploitable assets and services by SMEs. • Participation in at least 2 industrial exhibitions and conferences per year. • Promotion of the project at exhibitions and conferences. • Liaison with relevant European associations and Technology Platforms (e.g., 6G-IA, NESSI, NEM, NGI, NetWorld2020, Vision2020, CARIE). • Leadership of impact maximization activities of the project. • Development of the project's website and social media channels. • Contribution to the publishing of press releases, social media posts and web articles. • Co-organization of joint events with other SNS-JU projects. • Identification of synergies, common topics and collaboration for the promotion of the projects' results.

HPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication of project achievements through company's marketing channels such as website, professional social network and press releases. • Use of external tools such as press articles and blogs. • Advertising of the project at exhibitions and fairs like Mobile World Congress (MWC), Critical Communications World (CCW), EuCNC, Edge Computing Congress, AWS ReInvent and more. • Participation in events for the general public and university career/open days. • Participation in international scientific conferences and journals.
APPART	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of project results via available communication means such as the company's official website and social media and the utilization of informative newsletters in ICT domain. • Making the project known to network of customers and partners. • Utilization of any other opportunity for dissemination during project implementation.
F6S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of its platform with 4.7 million users and 1.6 million tech startups for promotion of 6G-PATH open calls. • Promotion of opportunities and outcomes through social media accounts. • Participation in conferences/events aligned with technology and addressed sectors.
OROF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration of usefulness of 6G-PATH networks in two schools in Romania. • Development of immersive education resources and training of teachers to use immersive education resources. • Collaboration with education authorities and organizations. • Dissemination of results at national and international events. • Organization of workshops and training sessions for teachers. • Collection of feedback from teachers and parents to improve content and teaching methods. • Participation in conferences organized by the Faculty of Education Sciences in Bucharest. • Collaboration with education specialists to present project's activities and achievements.
CHAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of project results at conferences and symposia through poster presentations and lectures. • Results to be featured on Charité's public website. • Results in peer-reviewed scientific journals. • Incorporation of project results into lectures at the Charité and the Evangelisches Geriatriezentrum Berlin.
MCS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set of messaging formats developed by MCS including newsletters, press releases and social media posts. • Dissemination of news or innovation relevant to target audience as "news event". • Adoption or reformatting of news generated by the consortium for MCS's purposes. • Use of publicly available channels such as social media and websites. • Utilization of MCS's own tools such as expert and user panels, surveys and workshops. • Dissemination of information and gathering of feedback from target audience. • Range of dissemination strategies and channels to be employed, aiming to maximize impact and reach of project results and outputs and ensuring accessibility and understandability to intended audience.
CSIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of results in plant science-related scientific journals such as Plant Physiology, New Phytologist, Nature Plants, Integrative and Comparative Biology, The Plant Journal, Physiologia Plantarum and Frontiers in Plant Science.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of results at international scientific conferences such as Plant Vascular Biology, Gordon Conferences on Vascular transport, International Society of Horticultural Science and Botanical Society of America. • Dissemination of results to countries from tropical regions such as Latin America and Asian countries (Australia, New Zealand, Japan and Vietnam) as well as to recent collaborators in Mediterranean basin, such as Algeria, Tunisia or Egypt. • Fruticulture Department as coordinator of CYTED network, a network of 11 countries, to be at the front of digitalization in fruticulture. • Inclusion of numerous private companies worldwide in dissemination plans such as companies in Spain like ANECOOP, Ruchey Cooperative, Grupo Medina, Westfalia Technological Services, Allesbeste and Brokaw and other international companies.
ACTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of information about activities and projects through the utilization of available communication channels. • Sharing of findings through joint publications with project partners whenever possible.
TER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination of activities and projects through various communication channels. • Provision of results into joint paper publications where opportunity arises.
UWS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on making significant contribution to new knowledge in scientific/academic communities through high-quality, peer-reviewed publications in leading international journals and magazines, e.g., IEEE Transactions on Services Computing, Cloud Computing, Mobile Computing, IEEE Communications Magazines, Wireless Communications, etc. • Focus on making significant contribution to new knowledge in scientific/academic communities through high-quality, peer-reviewed publications in leading international conferences, e.g., IEEE ICC, Globecom, WCNC, ICCE, etc. – several Best Paper Awards for UWS in recent international conferences. • Exhibition and promotion of pilot project demos in national and international venues like Glasgow Science Fair, demo track of conferences, etc. • Participation in various open days and technical events organized by UWS, UK, European and international stakeholders such as UK Research Councils, IEEE, IET, KTN (Knowledge Transfer Network), InnovateUK, SICSA (Scottish Informatics and Computer Science Alliance), the Royal Society, standardization bodies, etc. • Promotion of research conducted • Enablement of engagement of new beneficiaries. • Creation of new educational and industrial links.
UBRAD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted dissemination activities for: 1) the UK scientific and academic community, including staff and students in the Higher Education sector, 2) technical specialists and research professionals in industry, that are part of the UBRAD corporate partner community, including large telecom and network operators and service providers, and policy makers in local and central government. • Engagement of academic, scientific and student communities in the HE sector, through programmes of study, PhD research opportunities, workshops, and conferences attended by the UBRAD team in the UK and globally. • Utilization of journal editorship experience for organizing special issues of research journals on the theme of 6G, publishing project findings, collaborating with partners, involving the wider academic/scientific community and exposing project findings globally. • Utilization of the UBRAD academic network with over 100 international partners including top global universities and Fortune 100 technology-focused companies in the EMEA region,

facilitating the dissemination of project newsletter and publications, as well as invitation of stakeholders to project consortium events.

Overall, the efforts of each partner in disseminating the project's activities, results, impact and innovative aspects will run complementarily and will be crucial for achieving our ultimate goal. By leveraging our diverse expertise and networks, we aim to maximize the visibility and impact of the project across various stakeholders and communities. Through collaborative dissemination efforts, we can ensure that the pioneering work undertaken within the project reaches its intended audience, fostering greater awareness, engagement and advancement in our shared objectives.

3 Communication activities

This chapter outlines the communication strategies to be employed throughout the project duration, detailing the intended audience, goals and preferred communication channels. In general, the primary objectives of 6G-PATH communication initiatives will centre around enhancing public awareness and trust. These efforts will prioritize interactivity to engage audiences effectively, emphasizing outcomes and catering to specific local markets or communities to leverage established business networks or brand familiarity. Additionally, marketing strategies informed by corporate practices will be incorporated into communication endeavours to promote the 6G-PATH framework.

3.1 Communication target groups

Table 6 below presents the target audience for the collaborative communication strategy of 6G-PATH, along with the communication activities aimed at optimizing the project’s visibility. It should be noted, however, that these target groups are on top of the ones identified under the main dissemination target stakeholders.

Table 6: Communication target groups and respective activities

Main communication target groups	Activities
Non-specialized audience, general public, policy makers	Online publishing (online magazines, newspapers, blogs)
Non-specialized audience, general public, policy makers	Inclusion of light content for non-specialized audience in the project website, blog, social media, as well as publishing “lighter” versions of project newsletters, leaflets, flyers, etc.
Non-specialized audience, general public, policy makers	Participation in media (TV, newspapers, radio) events to communicate 6G-PATH results of the project and explain its benefits to EU citizens, industry etc.
Non-specialized audience, general public	6G-PATH news will appear in blogs and websites targeting non-specialized audience, especially the youngest one, focusing on technology news and trends

3.2 Communication channels

The comprehensive communication strategy adopted by 6G-PATH complements the dissemination strategy outlined in the previous chapter. The communication strategy integrates both conventional and innovative communication avenues, including:

3.2.1 Online publishing

Online publishing (also including online magazines, newspapers and blogs), serves as a dynamic communication strategy for disseminating and communicating project information. By partnering with these platforms or contributing guest articles, 6G-PATH will share insights, research findings and project updates with a diverse global audience. Online publishing offers a flexible and interactive medium for engaging stakeholders, fostering discussions and generating interest in the project’s activities and achievements. Through the strategic use of online publishing channels, 6G-PATH enhances its visibility, establishes thought leadership and effectively communicates its mission to a broader community.

3.2.2 Light material for non-specialized audience in the project website, blog, and social media

Light material tailored for a non-specialized audience will serve as a communication channel on various platforms, such as the project website, blog and social media. This content is designed to convey project updates, key findings and relevant information in a simplified and accessible manner. By utilizing concise language, visuals and engaging

formats, such as infographics or short videos, the project can effectively reach a broader audience beyond specialized stakeholders. These materials aim to increase awareness, generate interest and facilitate understanding of the project's objectives, activities and impacts among individuals with varying levels of expertise or interest in the field. They serve as an essential component of the project's communication strategy, ensuring that information is easily digestible and engaging for all audiences.

3.2.3 Newsletters

A minimum of 6 newsletters will be circulated across various mailing lists to facilitate communication with relevant research initiatives, projects, technical communities and the wider public. These newsletters, accessible on the project website, will offer updates on project activities, accomplishments and outcomes, with the aim of promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange. A Mailchimp account has been established for newsletter distribution, seamlessly linked to the project website.

3.2.4 Press releases

6G-PATH will publish more than 5 press releases to highlight major achievements and showcase the potential of 6G as a future-proof technology for health, education, farming and smart cities, focusing on the project's "key" milestones and advancements. These releases aim to generate interest among media outlets, industry stakeholders and the general public, raising awareness of the project's impact and positioning 6G as a transformative solution for addressing societal challenges and driving innovation. An initial press release was published in M2 (February 2024), featuring the project's kick-off meeting and providing an overview of the project's objectives, activities, and partners. The press release is available on the project website at: <https://6gpath.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Press-release-1-February-2024.pdf>

3.2.5 Leaflets

At least 2 leaflets will be prepared to effectively communicate its objectives, activities and achievements to various stakeholders. The first project leaflet has already been developed, showcasing "key" project information in a concise and engaging format (see Figures 14 and 15 below). This initial leaflet serves as a blueprint for future materials, providing a glimpse into the project's vision, goals and impact. Through the distribution of leaflets at conferences, workshops and other events, 6G-PATH aims to raise awareness, generate interest and foster engagement among target audiences.

Figure 14: 6G-PATH leaflet 1 – outer pages

Figure 15: 6G-PATH leaflet 1 – inner pages

3.2.6 Flyers

6G-PATH will produce at least 2 flyers to effectively communicate its key information. Of the first two flyers already prepared, one succinctly outlines the project’s rationale, objectives and consortium (Figure 16), while the other provides substantial information about the project’s open call #1 (Figure 17):

6G-Path | #6gpath | @6gpath | www.6gpath.eu

6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe

The path towards 6G is beginning now that 5G matured and is being deployed worldwide both publicly and privately. While 5G brought a step up in many fields, such as performance and efficiency, more is always expected in terms of efficiency by the overall community and in terms of performance by industry and technology providers who want to further increase their offerings and products. Continuous demands for higher throughput, lower latency and more energy efficient communications needs to be supported by relevant use cases that can claim and demonstrate the needs for these requests.

6G-PATH Objectives

1. Setup the 6G-PATH experiment and validation infrastructure and evolve it into 5G/6G experimental infrastructures and pre-normative testbeds.
2. Deliver and refine a transversal integration and experimentation platform.
3. Expand user community and implement large scale field trials with internal and external experiments, through Open Calls.
4. Collect and refine of requirements stemming from Stream B and verticals.
5. Devise leading-edge business models towards the commercialisation and exploitation of 6G-PATH use cases and technologies.
6. Disseminate and communicate results to a wide community of stakeholders while ensuring impact on standardisation efforts.
7. Create repositories for both open knowledge transfer and supporting the subsequent phases of the Smart Networks and Services (SNS) programme.

Consortium

OTC	Telecom	Orange	Telefónica	altice	AIRBUS
UNIVERSITY OF BOURGOGNE	Fraunhofer	UNIVERSITY OF BOURGOGNE	INSTITUTO DE TELECOMUNICACIONES	ONESOURCE	RedZinc
Odin	eBOS	Hewlett Packard Enterprise	APP	FGS	Fundatia
CHARITÉ	MCS	CSIC	ACTA	terrawave	CloudSigma
		UNIVERSITY OF WULFENBURG	UNIVERSITY OF BRADFORD		

Co-funded by the European Union | SNS | 6G-PATH project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS-JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139172. Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/>

Figure 16: 6G-PATH general flyer

6G-Path | #6gpath | @6gpath | www.6gpath.eu

6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe

Shape the future of connectivity and innovation with Beyond 5G/6G networks

Apply to 6G-PATH's Open Call #1 and secure funding to contribute to the development of 6G-infrastructure and related services and applications

- €1.2 million for the development of:
 - 2 new testbeds for additional use case scenarios or technology validation
 - 10 extensions to integrate into existing project testbeds.
- Funds available for academia, telecom operators, RTOs, startups and SMEs willing to contribute to the development of 6G-infrastructure and related services and applications.
- Business and technical support provided to facilitate technology deployment, integration test & validation.

Submissions open from
01 September 2024 to 31 October 2024

Consortium

OTC	Telecom	Orange	Telefónica	altice	AIRBUS
UNIVERSITY OF BOURGOGNE	Fraunhofer	UNIVERSITY OF BOURGOGNE	INSTITUTO DE TELECOMUNICACIONES	ONESOURCE	RedZinc
Odin	eBOS	Hewlett Packard Enterprise	APP	FGS	Fundatia
CHARITÉ	MCS	CSIC	ACTA	terrawave	CloudSigma
		UNIVERSITY OF WULFENBURG	UNIVERSITY OF BRADFORD		

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Figure 17: 6G-PATH open call #1 flyer

3.2.7 Media participation

6G-PATH will participate in at least 5 events in TV, newspapers and radio to showcase the innovative aspects of the project and major achievements. One notable media participation includes the feature of the 6G-PATH project through its partner Karlstad University, in SVT Nyheter, Sweden. The relevant information is available on the project website at: <https://6gpath.eu/6g-path-featured-in-svt-nyheter-sweden/>

3.2.8 6G-PATH news in blogs and websites

6G-PATH will disseminate project updates and information through online platforms that cater to a non-specialized audience, with a particular emphasis on younger demographics interested in technology news and trends. This approach aims to engage a broader audience and raise awareness of the project's innovations and advancements in the field of 6G technology. The activities undertaken in this direction so far are:

Table 7: 6G-PATH news in blogs and websites so far

Partner	Title of online news	Place of publication (blog, website)	Name of blog or website	Date of publication	No. of reads (as of 13.06.2024)	Link/Screenshot
UBRAD	6G roll-out role for University of Bradford	Website	University of Bradford website	02/02/24	149	https://www.bradford.ac.uk/news/archive/2024/6g-roll-out-role-for-university-of-bradford.php
eBOS	6G-PATH project kick-off meeting	Website	eBOS website	05/02/24	9	https://ebos.com.cy/6g-path-project-kick-off-meeting/
Altice Labs	6G-PATH: Kick-off meeting	Blog	Altice Labs internal blog	19/02/2024	43	<p>Comunicação</p> <p>6G-PATH: Kick-off meeting</p> <p>Posted on February 19, 2024 by comunicação</p> <p>Nos dias 30 e 31 de janeiro, Altice foi palco da reunião de kick-off do projeto "6G-PATH (6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe)", que contou com a forte presença dos membros do consórcio. Filipe Cabral Pinto, da direção de Estratégia de Inovação e Digital (EID), representou a Altice Labs no evento, efetuando uma apresentação relativa à testbed. É de salientar que o demonstrador de Aveiro é um use case de smart cities, desenvolvido em colaboração com o Instituto de Telecomunicações, tendo como objetivo evoluir a mobilidade das cidades com o apoio de redes de comunicação avançadas, bem como através de serviços de inteligência artificial.</p> <p>Ao longo do evento, cada um dos parceiros fez uma pequena reflexão relativa ao seu trabalho e o responsável pelo projeto partilhou ideias, discutindo-se também alguns aspetos administrativos. Foram ainda realizadas variadas sessões relativas a temas como a plataforma 6G-PATH, o ambiente de experimentação, a disseminação e comercialização, a gestão de dados, a inovação, os direitos de propriedade intelectual e a experimentação vertical.</p> <p>Este programa, oficialmente lançado a 1 de janeiro de 2024, resulta de um esforço de colaboração ao longo de 36 meses, assumindo-se como um passo significativo para o avanço da tecnologia.</p> <p>This entry was posted in Altice Labs, Projetos de Inovação and tagged 6G-PATH, Inteligência Artificial, Mobilidade, Smart Cities.</p>
KAU	Enhancing health education with the help of 6G	Website	Karlstad University website	08/03/24	114	https://www.kau.se/en/news/enhancing-health-education-help-6g

<p>Altice Labs</p>	<p>Altice Labs participates in the meeting of the 6G-PATH project</p>	<p>Blog</p>	<p>Altice Labs internal blog</p>	<p>27/05/2024</p>	<p>80</p>	<p>Comunicação</p> <p>Altice Labs participa na reunião do projeto 6G-PATH</p> <p>Posted on May 27, 2024 by comunicação</p> <p>O Instituto de Telecomunicações (IT) de Aveiro foi o palco, nos dias 14 e 15 de maio de 2024, da primeira reunião plenária do 6G-PATH, que reuniu os parceiros do projeto.</p> <p>Durante o evento, foram abordados vários temas destacando-se a evolução da arquitetura da plataforma e respetivas verticais, bem como o ambiente de experimentação para os diferentes casos de uso. De salientar ainda a demonstração efetuada pelo IT do carro autónomo, que será utilizado ao longo do 6G-PATH.</p> <p>Filipe Cabral Pinto e Miguel Mesquita, ambos da Direção de Innovation Strategy and Communication da Altice Labs, marcaram presença no evento, representando a empresa nesta reunião plenária. A Altice Labs está envolvida no desenvolvimento de uma testbed B5G, destinada a testar serviços avançados para as cidades do futuro, com particular ênfase para as questões de mobilidade apoiada por inteligência artificial.</p> <p>This entry was posted in Eventos, Projetos de Inovação and tagged 6G-PATH, Cidades do Futuro, Inteligência Artificial, Mobilidade, Reunião, Testbed B5G.</p>
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In conclusion, the coordinated efforts of all partners in implementing the communication strategy will be instrumental in achieving the project’s overarching objectives. By capitalizing on diverse expertise and networks, the communication activities along with dissemination activities aim to enhance visibility and impact across various stakeholders and communities. Through collaborative communication initiatives, the innovative work undertaken within the project will effectively reach its intended audience, fostering heightened awareness, engagement and progress towards shared goals.

4 Awareness raising strategy

In order to ensure the success and impact of the 6G-PATH project, a robust awareness raising strategy has been devised. This strategy aims to elevate awareness about the project’s objectives, scope and technological advancements among “key” stakeholders, industry players, potential users and the broader community. By strategically disseminating information and fostering engagement, the project envisions to position itself as a pioneering initiative in the realm of 6G technology development and deployment.

4.1 Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy

The Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy is the cornerstone of our awareness raising efforts. It outlines the “key” elements and activities that will guide our efforts to effectively promote the 6G-PATH project. The main components of the D&C strategy are:

- Target audiences: Identifying “key” stakeholders, industry players, potential users and the broader community who will benefit from and contribute to the project.
- Communication tools: Utilizing a mix of traditional and digital media, including press releases, social media, webinars, conferences and scientific publications, to disseminate information.
- Roles and responsibilities: Assigning specific roles to team members and collaborators to ensure a coordinated and efficient implementation of the strategy.
- “Key” messages: Crafting clear and compelling messages that highlight the objectives, scope and technological advancements of the 6G-PATH project.
- Feedback mechanisms: Establishing channels for receiving and incorporating feedback from stakeholders to refine and improve our communication efforts.

4.2 6G-PATH awareness raising strategy phases

The 6G-PATH awareness raising strategy is designed in three distinct phases to effectively promote the project’s objectives, scope and technological advancements. These phases are detailed in the table below:

Table 8: 6G-PATH awareness raising strategy phases

Phase 1: Project Promotion (M1-M12)	
Description	“Key” activities
During this initial phase, the focus is on laying the groundwork for project promotion and creating initial awareness in relevant markets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination and Communication Strategy: Agreeing upon a comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy to guide future activities. • Market Awareness: Initiating efforts to create awareness among stakeholders in markets related to the project's objectives and scope.
Phase 2: Project Commercialization (M13-M26)	
Description	“Key” activities
In this phase, the focus shifts towards targeted awareness-raising activities aimed at “key” players, potential users, and experimenters.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted Awareness: Creating focused awareness campaigns to highlight 6G-PATH technologies among key stakeholders. • Technology Benefits: Informing the target market and experimenters about the technological advantages and benefits offered by 6G-PATH.

Phase 3: Project Promotion (M27-M36 and >M36)	
Description	“Key” activities
The final phase is centred on maximizing market and industry awareness of the 6G-PATH system to ensure project sustainability and full exploitation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Maximization: Implementing strategies to maximize target market and industry awareness regarding the 6G-PATH system. • Sustainability and Exploitation: Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project and fully exploiting its potential through effective business strategies.

The awareness raising strategy outlined in this chapter lays the foundation for the successful promotion and impact of the 6G-PATH project. By strategically navigating through three “key” phases – Project Promotion, Project Commercialization and Business Strategy – the project aims to elevate awareness and engagement among stakeholders at various levels.

As the project progresses, continual refinement and adaptation of the awareness raising strategy will be essential to ensure alignment with evolving project goals and stakeholder needs. By remaining agile and responsive to feedback, the 6G-PATH project is poised to make significant strides in advancing 6G technology and addressing societal challenges in the digital age.

5 Dissemination and Communication guidelines

This chapter outlines the guidelines for Dissemination and Communication, encompassing both internal and external communication aspects. It is imperative that all partners of 6G-PATH adhere to these guidelines to ensure consistency in representation, efficient internal coordination, and alignment with the objectives outlined in the GA.

5.1 Internal Communication

Effective internal communication is crucial for the seamless execution of the 6G-PATH project. The following elements are “key” to ensuring robust internal communication among consortium partners:

- **WP meetings:** Regular meetings are held for each work package (WP) to ensure ongoing coordination and visibility. For instance, WP7 conducts monthly meetings to discuss progress, address issues and plan upcoming dissemination and communication activities.
- **Communication tracker tool:** A shared tracking tool is being used to document and monitor all dissemination and communication activities. This tool is accessible to all partners via the project’s shared platform, enabling transparency and collaboration.
- **Data repository:** A centralized repository has been established for sharing documents, data and other resources relevant to the project. This repository facilitates easy access and retrieval of information for all consortium members.
- **Close contact with trials/pilots:** Regular updates and close communication are being maintained with teams conducting trials and pilots to ensure that dissemination and communication activities are aligned with the project’s value propositions and real-world applications.
- **Advisory Board:** The Advisory Board, managed under WP1, plays a critical role in guiding the project and communicating outputs. It consists of project experts who provide strategic advice, ensure alignment with industry standards and assist in disseminating “key” findings and advancements. Regular meetings with the Advisory Board help in refining the project’s direction and enhancing its impact through well-informed dissemination strategies.

5.2 Email addresses for 6G-PATH dissemination and communication activities

To facilitate coordination and communication among partners, a structured email distribution list has been established. This ensures relevant information is disseminated efficiently and to the appropriate audience. The email distribution list is as follows:

Table 9: 6G-PATH mailing lists

all@6gpath.eu	General Communications
project.brd@6gpath.eu	Project Board Issues
technical.brd@6gpath.eu	Technical Board Issues
legal@6gpath.eu	Legal Issues
financial@6gpath.eu	Financial Issues
wp1@6gpath.eu	WP1 Communications
wp2@6gpath.eu	WP2 Communications
wp3@6gpath.eu	WP3 Communications

wp4@6gpath.eu	WP4 Communications
wp5@6gpath.eu	WP5 Communications
wp6@6gpath.eu	WP6 Communications
wp7@6gpath.eu	WP7 Communications

With regard to WP7 in particular, the respective mailing list (wp7@6gpath.eu) serves as a regular platform for disseminating information and other important activities to all WP7 partners. Should any consortium partner have specific inquiries not addressed within the designated sections, they may utilize the aforementioned mailing list to contact the WP7 leader while, simultaneously, notifying all individuals responsible for dissemination activities across partner organizations.

The partner that is responsible for managing all mailing lists associated with the 6G-PATH project is ONE.

5.3 Announcements of upcoming publications

The 6G-PATH project relies on the scientific dissemination of project outcomes by its consortium partners. To facilitate this process, the guidelines outlined below provide a systematic approach:

Preparation of Abstract/Paper/Poster:

- Obtain permission for publication from all involved parties if the content includes contributions from other consortium members.
- Submit the publication (or a short abstract in the case of a scientific publication) to wp7@6gpath.eu, including the venue, date, link, attending auditorium, and the document for planned publication (at least 45 days before submission).

Notification and Objections:

- Consortium members may raise objections within 30 days of notification via wp7@6gpath.eu or directly with the publishing partner. Silence implies agreement.
- Objections should specify necessary modifications and involve discussions between the publishing and objecting parties.
- Publications should not be delayed more than 4 months after objections are resolved.

Revision:

- If objections are raised, publications must be revised accordingly, with new notifications to the consortium as needed.

Funding Acknowledgement:

- All publications must include the funding acknowledgement for the 6G-PATH project as follows: *“6G-PATH project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139172.”*

Documentation and Updates:

- Add publication details to the Dissemination and Communication tracking tool available at the project's shared platform and regularly update the project website with this information.

- Inform the consortium via wp7@6gpath.eu of event attendance representing the 6G-PATH project, facilitating collaboration among members – this point applying to all cases.

6 Dissemination and Communication metrics and quantifiable targets

This chapter outlines the metrics for dissemination and communication. Detailed reports on dissemination and communication activities will be provided in the upcoming deliverables D7.3 and D7.4. At the same time, the project website (<https://6gpath.eu>) is constantly updated with the latest significant dissemination and communication endeavours. The achieved dissemination activities so far are also presented in relevant tables. The following table provides the relevant dissemination and communication activities along with their respective target values.

Table 10: 6G-PATH dissemination and communication activities and metrics

Activity/Metrics		Overall target	Achieved (as of 13.06.2024)	
Dissemination activities	Workshops at conferences	Workshops organised (≥ 2 /year)	≥ 6	1
		Participants in each workshop	~ 50	20
	On-site demonstrations	Demonstrations and showcase events	≥ 8	4 (1/4 forthcoming)
	Scientific papers in workshops, conferences, and journals	Workshop papers published (> 4 /year)	> 12	-
		Conference papers published (> 6 /year)	> 18	2
		Journal papers published (> 4 /year)	> 12	2
	Social networks (LinkedIn, YouTube, X)	6G-PATH posts	≥ 10	45 (including 11 reposts)
		Contacts	≥ 100	241
		Likes	≥ 50	449
		Comments	≥ 2	3
	Participation in trade fairs	Project brochure copies delivered	≥ 10	-
	Project website	Online available	M3	YES
		Top 5 Search Engine (SEPR) > 100 monthly visitors to the website	> 3600	161
	Open events with free access	Open events/Hands-on workshops and tutorials for experimenters and public in general	> 8	-
Clustering activities and knowledge transfer meetings	Other on-going and to start research activities (> 6 /year)	> 18	-	
Open access datasets from project internal and third-party experiments made available	Datasets released in open access	> 50	-	

	Corporate Design/Branding	Project identity	1	1
	Printed material and posters	Number of posters & roll-up banners	>3	7&1
	Project brochure	Number of hardcopies	1000	-
Communication activities	Online publishing (online magazines, newspapers, blogs)	Publications/year	≥5	-
		Views	≥ 500	-
	Light content for non-specialized audience: Light material for non-specialized audience in the project website, blog, social media, and “lighter” versions of project newsletters, leaflets, flyers, etc.; Target value: ≥5	Number of light material items for non-specialized audience in the project website, blog, social media	>3	-
		Number of newsletters	≥6	-
		Press releases	>5	1
		Leaflets	≥2	1
		Flyers	≥2	2

	Participation in media (TV, newspapers, radio) events	Media appearances	≥5	1
	6G-PATH news in blogs and websites	6G-PATH news will appear in blogs and websites targeting non-specialized audience; reads per communication	≥100	395

In the tables that follow, the details of the major dissemination activities that have been achieved are presented. These include workshops organized at conferences, demonstrations and showcase events, published conference papers, and journal papers.

Table 11: Workshops at conferences organized

Partner(s)	Title of conference	Place, date	Workshop title	Number of participants	Links to activity
ONE, ICT-FI	IEEE International Conference on Communications (9-13 June 2024)	Denver, Colorado, USA, 9/06/2024	2nd International Workshop on Intelligent Cloud Continuum for 5G Services	20	https://6g-cloud-continuum-workshop.net/icc2024/ https://6gpath.eu/6g-path-workshop-in-icc2024/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206191354568134656

Table 12: Demonstrations and showcase events

Partner(s)	Partner role	Title of demonstration/ showcase event	Place, Date	Organiser	Links to activity
OTE, ONE	Present the project at a booth	EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024	Antwerp, Belgium, 3-6/6/2024	Coordination and Support Action 6GStart, Project HEU-CL4-2021-101069987	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203678429102125056 https://6gpath.eu/6g-path-at-eucnc-6g-summit-2024/
F6S	Showcase the project at a booth	Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition	Lisbon, Portugal, 27-29/5/2024	dmg events	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7202230357155266561 https://6gpath.eu/6g-path-at-the-lisbon-energy-summit-exhibition-2024
UWS	Introduction of the 6G-PATH project in an invited speech titled "AI for 6G network management"	ITU AI for Good Global Summit	Geneva, Switzerland, 30-31/5/2024	ITU in partnership with 40 UN Sister Agencies and co-convener	https://aiforgood.itu.int/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203289201952333824

	and control optimization”			with Switzerland	
ONE, OTE	Showcase the project at a booth	12th FOKUS FUSECO Forum	Berlin, Germany, 7-8/11/ 2024	Fraunhofer FOKUS	https://www.fokus.fraunhofer.de/ngni/events/fuseco-forum_2024/

Table 13: Conference papers published

Partner(s)	Title of paper	Title of conference	Date of submission	Full paper reference (APA)
FOKUS, CHAR	5G Wound Management System for Remote Areas	4th IEEE International Conference on ICT Solutions for eHealth (ICT4eHealth)	20/2/2024	Ancuta, Corici, A., Lahmann, N., Corici, M., Hoquel-Hans, M., Kuntz, S., Häusler, B., Deter, A., Grohnert, A. & Zope, H. (2024). 5G Wound Management System for Remote Areas. 4th IEEE International Conference on ICT Solutions for eHealth, ICT4eHealth, ESIEE Paris, France, 26-29 June 2024
OTE (incl. All partners)	Promoting Deployment of Innovative Use Cases in Market Verticals for the support of 6G Evolution: The 6G-PATH Context	AIAI 2024 – 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Application and Innovations/5G-PINE	9/04/2024	Chochliouros, I. et al. (2024). Promoting Deployment of Innovative Use Cases in Market Verticals for the support of 6G Evolution: The 6G-PATH Context. <i>20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations, AIAI 2024</i> , Ionian University, Corfu, Greece, 27-30 June, 2024, Proceedings

Table 14: Journal papers published

Partner(s)	Title of paper	Name of journal	Date of submission	Link to publication	Full paper reference (APA)
ICT-FI	On Covert Rate in Full-Duplex D2D-Enabled Cellular Networks with Spectrum Sharing and Power Control	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	08/03/2024	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10461647	Sun, R., Wu, H., Yang, B., Shen, Y., Yang, W., Jiang, X., & Taleb, T. (2024). On Covert Rate in Full-Duplex D2D-Enabled Cellular Networks with Spectrum Sharing and Power Control. <i>IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing</i> , 1-15. https://doi.org/10.1109/TMC.2024.3371377
ICT-FI	Federated Deep Reinforcement Learning for Prediction-Based Network Slice Mobility in 6G Mobile Networks	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	22/05/2024	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10536643	Ming, Z., Yu, H., & Taleb, T. (2024). Federated Deep Reinforcement Learning for Prediction-Based Network Slice Mobility in 6G Mobile Networks. <i>IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing</i> , 1-17.

The project's DCM (eBOS) has developed a Dissemination and Communication activity report Excel file, accessible via the project's shared platform. This file serves as a means for partners to document their involvement in communication and dissemination activities. The DCM is tasked with incorporating the reported activities into the D&C tracking tool, which is a comprehensive system designed to monitor all dissemination and communication activities against their Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring continuous updates to reflect the current status. The D&C tracking tool is also accessible via the project's shared platform.

7 Next actions and conclusions

The deliverable D7.2 has provided a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication strategies implemented within the 6G-PATH project. Beginning with a discussion of dissemination activities, target groups and channels, the document progressed to communication activities and their corresponding target groups and channels, followed by an overview of the awareness raising strategy aimed at promoting the project objectives and technological advancements.

Guidelines for conducting dissemination and communication activities, including email addresses and announcements, were provided. Additionally, metrics and quantifiable targets for monitoring outcomes associated with dissemination and communication activities were outlined.

Overall, through concerted efforts to create initial awareness, target specific audiences and maximize market and industry awareness, the 6G-PATH project endeavours to position itself as a frontrunner in 6G technology development. By effectively disseminating information about its objectives, scope, and technological advancements, the project seeks to catalyse innovation, foster collaboration and, ultimately, “drive” the adoption of 6G technologies.

To conclude, this deliverable serves as a foundation for forthcoming reports, namely D7.3 and D7.4, titled “Dissemination, Commercialization, and Standardization” (initial and final versions respectively). These reports will offer comprehensive insights into the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the project’s duration.

References

[1] 6G-PATH (“6G Pilots and TriAls THrough Europe”) Project, Grant Agreement No.101139172, <https://6gpath.eu>